

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

UZBEK COMMERCIAL BANKS ACTIVITY AS INSTITUTIONAL INVESTORS

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ABSTRACT

The activities of banks were systematically studied as institutional investors in the securities market in the article. In the article, since commercial banks operating in our country are supposed to gradually increase the minimum amount of authorized capital to five hundred billion soums until 2025 in accordance with the current legislation, the tasks that Uzbekistan needs to implement within the framework of the banking system reform strategy and the development strategy have been researched. In order to improve the investment activity of banks, the shares issued as issuers in the securities market, their share among institutional investors, and the current situation of the contribution of large joint-stock companies are studied in the article. It was studied the strategy for reforming the banking system of Uzbekistan with the support of international financial institutions, the provision of gradual privatization of State shares in "Uzsanoatqurilishbank", "Asaka" "Ipoteka-Bank", "Alaqabank", "Qishloq qurilish bank" and "Turonbank", which are considered large banks in Uzbekistan in terms of the amount of capital and assets, the volume of credit and deposit portfolios.

Keywords: stock market, institutional investor, banks, commercial bank, investment banks, investment funds, ordinary share, preferred share, "Tashkent" RFB. deposits, capitalization.

Introduction. Institutional investors operate in the stock market of economically developed countries, and their services are mainly used by banks, insurance companies, pension and investment funds. In this case, commercial banks can also participate as an issuer by issuing securities, as an investment intermediary in the formation of acceptable categories of equity investment (mainly mutual) funds in stock market trading, and as an investor in stock market trading. By supporting the technical and technological renewal of the economy of our republic, sharply increasing its competitiveness, increasing the export potential, establishing new enterprises based on innovative and energy-saving technologies, and financing enterprises producing new types of products in demand in the world market, the banking system is responsible for the consistent implementation of the state investment policy making a decent contribution.

The stock market also creates an opportunity for commercial banks to attract additional capital. They can attract authorized capital from the issue of securities, and money for the formation of credit resources. Commercial banks operating in our country today, in accordance with the current legislation [1], the minimum amount of bank charter capital will be one hundred billion soums from September 1, 2023. In the future, it is proposed to make additions to Article 13 of the Law "On Banks and Banking Activities" in order to increase the minimum amount of bank charter capital to five hundred billion soums by 2025. At the same time, it is established that the authorized capital of the bank will be formed in the national currency of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and it will be formed from the money contributed by the founders and shareholders of the bank or from the state's securities. This indicates that commercial banks are not only involved in the formation of authorized capital, but also accelerate their activities in the securities market as institutional investors.

Literature review on the topic: It is possible to emphasize the emergence of new financial institutions as a legitimate and objective result of the development of market relations. Commercial banks actively participating in the transformation of savings into investments can be recognized among such financial institutions. In international practice, the interpretation of the activity of institutional investors as an integral part of the stock market, according to U. Sharp, one of the leading economists in the world economy, "when discussing the increasing importance of institutional investors in the American stock market, the main attention is paid by pension funds, insurance companies, and trust operations departments of banks focused on the investments to be made. The total share of these organizations is more than half of the share capital issued by American corporations»[4]. This definition is specific to countries with developed economies, where alternative resources necessary for activity are attracted through financial market instruments. This indicates that the necessary funds for economic entities in developed countries are attracted through the activities of institutional investors such as commercial banks in the securities market.

In studies specific to commercial banks as institutional investors, according to scientists and experts, the perfect definition is Recommended by V.N Kolesnikov: He mentioned that it means "Various financial institutions (commercial and investment banks, insurance companies, pension funds) that carry out operations with securities"[5]. This approach is based on the idea that many of these institutions combine the funds of various investors (individuals and legal entities) to form commercial banks that seek the opportunity to invest them in valuable securities that bring income.

Uzbek economist-scientist A.T. Uzokov also interprets the investment activities of insurance companies as follows: "Institutional investors are specialists who are paid for managing someone's money. They are

employed by financial institutions, for example, banks, insurance companies, mutual and pension funds, as well as financial corporations, and in special cases - private (individual) individuals»[6]. In this definition, privatization investment funds, which acted as investment intermediaries in the privatization and expropriation of state property, were ignored. This indicates that due to the lack of research on the activities of commercial banks as institutional investors in the stock market in the economy of Uzbekistan, its scientific-theoretical foundations have not been studied in the financial literature.

Analysis and results.

Measures to expand the size of the stock market of our republic with the participation of institutional investors, that is, in the decree "On the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026", "gradual liberalization of capital movement in our country and privatization of large enterprises and their shares (shares), including through the stock exchange and State by the end of 2026, the share of the private sector in bank assets will be completed to 60%" and other actions relevant to the stock market, "in order to increase financial resources in the economy, the turnover of the stock market will increase from 200 million US dollars to 7 billion US dollars in the next 5 years»[2] is important in the analysis of increasing activity of commercial banks as institutional investors in the securities market.

Commercial banks operating as institutional investors (issuers) in Uzbekistan have a value of 60.3 trillion soums, equal to 33.7% of the total shares issued by joint-stock companies (JSC) of our country, and 96.7% of the total shares issued by institutional institutions. This situation is evaluated by the fact that commercial banks as institutional investors - issuers in our country

have reached the monopoly level in the securities market, and the high impact of the country's financial potential on stable economic growth rates. However, comparing the weight of the total shares issued by the financial sector with joint stock companies (JSC) operating in the economy of our republic, this share is 35.3%. This means that, as we mentioned above, most of the shares issued on the stock market of our country correspond to the share of the non-financial sector of the economy.

The main goal of the reforms in the banking sector of our republic is to meet the demand of the population for modern financial services and to increase the capitalization of commercial banks. The strategy of reforming the banking system of Uzbekistan in 2020-2025 adopted on the basis of the decree of the President of May 12, 2020[3] is of great importance in this regard. Based on it, with the support of international financial institutions, "Ipoteka-bank", "Uzsanoatqurilishbank", "Asaka", "Aloqabank", the state shares in "Qishloq Qurilish Bank" and "Turonbank" are supposed to be gradually privatized. Among these banks, "Uzsanoatqurilishbank" and "Asaka" banks are the second and third largest banks in Uzbekistan in terms of capital and assets, loan and deposit portfolios. Also, financial transactions carried out by banks through "issuing, purchasing, selling securities, keeping their accounts and keeping them, managing securities according to the contract concluded with the client, performing other operations with them"[1], banks are chartered the stock market (Tashkent RFB) plays an important role in the gradual increase of the minimum amount of capital, the issuing of additional shares and maintaining the quotation of shares.

Figure 1. As of April 1, 2023, shares issued by institutional investors of Uzbekistan and the contribution of large joint-stock commercial banks, in percent.

1 <https://deponet.uz>. Ma'lumotlari.

Figure 1 shows the analysis of shares issued by the banks of our republic as issuers in the securities market, their share among institutional investors, and the share of large joint-stock companies within banks.

As shown in Figure 1, as of April 1, 2023, 62.4 trillion soums worth of shares were put into circulation by the institutional investors of our republic, of which 96.4% or 60.3 trillion soums belonged to banks. This situation occurred due to the requirement to increase the authorized capital of commercial banks. Also, if we analyze the data of banks with a high share of shares issued in our Republic, the joint-stock commercial bank "Agrobank" has the highest share with 14.19%, having issued shares worth 8.6 trillion soums. In the next places, the volume of shares issued by "O'zbekiston Respublikasi aksiyadorlik tijorat Xalq Banki" is equal to 7.4 trillion soums and a 12.19% share, and "Asakabank" joint-stock company has 5.9 trillion soums and a 9.72% share, respectively. Although the remaining 31 joint-stock companies have put into circulation 38.4 billion soums worth of shares, their share in the total share is equal to 63.6%.

Investment funds that have a high position in the world stock market have little influence on our national economy, they only put into circulation 2.32 billion soums of shares, and the share of institutional investors is close to 0.01%, while the remaining 3.95% or more than 2.1 trillion soums belong to insurance companies. This indicates that the number of insurance companies as issuers was only 9 at the beginning of 2019, and now their number has reached 48, and the amount of shares issued by them has increased accordingly. Also, the main goal of the investment policy of commercial banks is to ensure the profitability of their funds, like other institutional investors.

The activity of "Tashkent" RFB in sales by the banks of our republic can be evaluated differently. In our republic, as well as banks of economically developed countries, in order to increase bank capitalization, they use stock market trading to maintain the quotation price of their ordinary and preferred shares. Therefore, we will consider the change in the price of shares of joint-stock commercial banks actively participating in RFB trades of our country "Tashkent" through their comparative analysis.

Table 1

As of May 22, 2023, a comparative analysis of the price of shares of joint-stock commercial banks (ATB) that actively participating in "Tashkent" RFB trading.

№	Name of banks	Nominal price of shares, in soums		Quotation price of shares, in soums		The difference between share prices,%	
		A common stock	Preferred stock	A common stock	Preferred stock	A common stock	Preferred stock
1	Hamkorbank ATB	5,0	5,0	125,01	75,35	25 EQ	15 EQ
2	Mikrokreditbank ATB	1 068,0	1 068,0	1 067,99	10 000,0	99,9	9,4 EQ
3	Qishloq Qurilish Bank ATB	119,25	119,25	112,42	5 100,0	94,3	42,8 EQ
4	Ipotekabank ATB	1,0	1,0	0,91	3,49	91,0	3,5 EQ
5	O'zsano-atqurilishbank ATB	19,0	19,0	10,1	38,0	53,2	2 EQ
6	Garantbank AJ	100,0	100,0	209,9	-	2 EQ	-
7	Aloqabank AT	121,0	121,0	82,0	550,0	67,8	4,5 EQ
8	Agrobank ATB	1 168,0	1 168,0	577,0	72 000,0	49,4	61,6 EQ
9	Universalbank ATB	5 000,0	-	13 390	-	2,7 EQ	-
10	Turonbank ATB	1 700,0	1 700,0	1 329,99	2 500,0	82,4	1,5 EQ

According to this table, as of May 22, 2023, mainly 10 banks actively participated in "Tashkent" RFB sales. The minimum nominal value of their ordinary shares was set at 1.0 soums (ATIB "Ipotekabank"), and the maximum nominal value was 5,000 soums (ATB "Universalbank"). If we pay attention to the sales of shares of "Tashkent" RFB by these issuers, the highest increase was recorded by ATB "Hamkorbank". That is, it indicates that the shares put into circulation by ATB "Hamkorbank" with a nominal value of 5 soums reached 125.01 soums by quoting at "Tashkent" RFB trades or increased 25 times as a result of capitalization. This may have been influenced by the announcement by the issuer that the dividend amount for the results of 2022 has been set at 30% compared to the nominal value. If the preferential share of this issue was put into circulation at a nominal value of 5 soums,

as a result of being quoted in the "Tashkent" RFB trades, the selling price reached 75 soums 35 tithes, or its capitalization increased up to 15 times. The increase in the value of these 2 types of shares in the stock market is due to the fact that ATB "Hamkorbank" has attracted additional financial resources important for its activities, on the one hand, the activity of commercial banks of our Republic as institutional investors in the trades of "Tashkent" RFB is increasing, on the other hand, as defined in the development strategy, financial in the economy in order to increase resources, it indicates that it participates in increasing the turnover of the stock market.

If we analyze the stock quotation of ATB "Mikrokreditbank" shares in the "Tashkent" RFB trading, although the value of ordinary shares has not changed (99.9%), the price of its preferred shares has

increased by 9.4 times to 10,000.0 soums. It is known that the dividend on ordinary shares is determined by the general meeting of shareholders, and its relatively low refinancing rate and almost unchanged quotation price may weaken investors' interest in these shares. On the contrary, the interest in preferred shares may be caused by the fact that their dividend is fixed and higher than the interest earned on bank deposits. However, according to the information on the ATB "Mikrokreditbank" website, in the following years, dividends on ordinary and preferred shares were not paid out of the net profit at the end of the year.

If we analyze the participation of ATB "Qishloq Qurilish Bank" in the stock exchange trading, the market price of ordinary shares with a nominal value of 119.25 soums decreased by 94.3% to 112.42 soums, compared to the nominal price of preferred shares, the market price is 42.8 doubled to 5,100 soums. According to the issuer's 2022 reports, no dividend was paid to the owners of ordinary shares, and 25.0% dividend was reported for preferred shares.

ATIB "Ipotekabank" nominal value of common and preferred shares was set at 1 soum, while its ordinary share fell to 91 tithes in the stock market, while the quotation of its preferred share increased by almost 3.5 times and rose to 3 soum 47 tyennes. According to the 2022 reports of this issuer, no dividend was paid to the owners of ordinary shares, and information was provided on the payment of 25.0% dividend on preferred shares.

ATB "Uzsanoatqurilishbank" is the second joint-stock bank in Uzbekistan in terms of capital and assets, loan and deposit portfolios, and its shares are put into circulation at the nominal value of 19.0 soums. Quotation of ordinary shares fell to 10.1 soums or 53.2% in stock market trading, on the contrary, the price of preferred shares increased by 2 times to 38 soums. In the reports of ATB "Uzsanoatqurilishbank" for 2022, even in this bank, no dividend was paid to the owners of ordinary shares, but 23.0% dividend payment is provided for preferred shares.

"Garantbank" joint-stock company (JSC), different from other banks, put into circulation only ordinary shares with a nominal value of 100 soums. The market price of this issuer's share is currently 209 soums or more than 2 times higher than the nominal value. The reason for saying this is that the share price can change (fluctuate) during the day based on supply and demand. That is, during the research period-day, the shares of this issuer were sold in the range of 192-209 soums. In the 2022 reports of "Garantbank" JSC, the payment of 30% of the nominal dividend to ordinary share holders can also be considered as a beneficial investment for investors.

If we analyze the stock quotation of "Aloqabank" shares in the "Tashkent" RFB sales, from shares with a nominal price of 121.0 soums, the value of its ordinary shares fell to 82.0 soums or 67.8%. the price increased by 4.5 times to 550.0 soums. According to the information on the website of AT "Aloqabank", in the next 2020-2022, dividends on ordinary and preferred shares have not been paid out of the net profit at the end of the year. Taking into account that preferred shares in banks

are placed mainly among employees, the overquotation of shares may be related to the bank's strategy.

If the nominal value of ordinary and preferred shares of ATB "Agrobank" is set at 1168.0 soums, its ordinary share in exchange trading has fallen to 577.0 soums or 49.4%, then the quotation of preferential shares has increased by almost 61.6 times and reached 72 00 soums. Also according to the 2022 reports of this issuer, ordinary stock holders are provided with a dividend payment of 292.0% on non-dividend shares (in soums per share) or 25.0% on preferred shares (in percentage per share face value). For the period 2009-2021, the bank has regularly paid 25% dividend to preferred stock holders. It is possible that this factor can cause the quotation of preferred shares to increase by up to 61.6 times.

ATB "Universalbank", just like "Garantbank" JSC, put into circulation only ordinary shares with a nominal value of 5,000 soums. The market price of this issuer's share is currently 13,390 soums or 2.7 times higher than the nominal value. In the reports of ATB "Universalbank" for 2022, the payment of 30% of the nominal dividend to the holders of ordinary shares can be considered as a beneficial investment for investors. The bank's information on important facts of the open-info.uz/uz site provides information on the payment of a dividend of 7.8% or 392.0 soums on preferred shares for 2022 (as a percentage of the nominal value of one share). Just as every bank has its own investment strategy, ATB Universalbank also has its own dividend policy.

At the end of our research, we will analyze the activity of ATB "Turonbank" in the stock market. The nominal price of shares of this bank is 1,700 soums. ATB "Turonbank" ordinary share fell to 1,329.99 soums or 82.4% in stock market trading, while the quotation of its preferred share increased by almost 1.5 times and reached 2,500 soums. According to the reports of this issuer for 2009-2020, if it paid dividends to the owners of ordinary shares in the range of 0-30% (in some years it was not paid at all), the bank regularly pays dividends to the owners of preferred shares in the amount of 20.0-43.0%. The dividend policy of this bank is unique among the banks of our republic.

We consider that the following conclusions and suggestions are appropriate for improving the activity of commercial banks of Uzbekistan as investment investors:

We believe that the following conclusions and suggestions are appropriate for improving the activity of commercial banks of Uzbekistan as investment investors:

1. The analysis of the investment activities of ATB "Khamkorbank" in the securities market shows that the activity of this bank as an institutional investor in "Tashkent" RFB trades has increased, and the quotation price of its shares has increased by 15-25 times compared to the nominal price. If such a practice is used in other banks, not only the capitalization of the stock market of our country will increase, as defined in the development strategy, but also the possibility of attracting additional financial resources necessary for the bank's activities will be created.

2. It is known that in the banks of a country with a developing economy like Uzbekistan, in most cases, the conclusion on the payment of income per common share is adopted based on their founding documents, based on the decision of the general meeting of shareholders in order to increase the bank's capitalization. The fact that the dividend for preferred shares is fixed and higher than the interest from bank deposits can be considered as a factor influencing the investment of funds by the population (investor). The data obtained during the research period, except for banks such as ATB "Mikrokreditbank" and ATB Aloqabank, unlike ordinary joint-stock companies, dividends on preferred shares were paid between 20-40 percent. Due to this reason, the market price of their preferred shares increased from 2 times to 61.6 times in "Tashkent" RFB sales.

3. Investors have long-term goals, so they need to rely on the database to protect themselves from market volatility and confusion, and to avoid dispersing their holdings even when activity in the stock markets slows down. Today openinfo.uz. in the information of the site about the important facts related to banks, the information about the bank's financial capabilities is not enough to fully imagine and make an investment decision. Therefore, it is necessary to create a daily in-

formation and analysis magazine (newspaper) or an internet site in our Republic, as in developed countries, in order to be aware of the situation of investors in the stock market trading, as well as the quotations and their analytical conclusions of the trading of bank shares.

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